

Supplemental Table S1. Strains used in this study.

Yeast strain	Genotype	Genotype reference
BY4741	<i>Mat a, leu2-Δ0, his3-Δ1, met15-Δ0, ura3-Δ0</i>	Euroscarf
<i>sus1Δ</i>	<i>Mat a, leu2-Δ0, his3-Δ1, met15-Δ0, ura3-Δ0 sus1::KANMX4</i>	This study
SUS1-TAP	<i>Mat a, leu2-Δ0, his3-Δ1, met15-Δ0, SUS1-TAP::URA3</i>	This study
SUS1-MYC	<i>Mat a, leu2-Δ0, his3-Δ1, met15-Δ0, ura3-Δ0, SUS1-MYC::HIS3</i>	Pascual-García et al. (2008)
SUS1-MYC <i>spt8Δ</i>	<i>Mat a, leu2-Δ0, his3-Δ1, met15-Δ0, ura3-Δ0, SUS1-MYC::HIS3, spt8::KanMX4</i>	This study
SUS1-MYC <i>spt7-1180</i>	<i>Mat a, leu2-Δ0, his3-Δ1, met15-Δ0, ura3-Δ0, SUS1-MYC::HIS3, spt7-1180::KanMX4</i>	This study